
CSCCE Glossary: Scientific Community Engagement Fundamentals

Introduction

[Scientific Community Engagement Fundamentals \(CEF\)](#) is CSCCE's foundational professional development training for STEM community managers. It is an eight-week course that explores core frameworks and defines a shared vocabulary to describe a community's purpose, refine or create strategic programming to engage community members around shared goals, and identify ways to lower barriers to member participation. This glossary compiles the terms used in the course that might be new to participants, as well as familiar terms that require definition in the context of community building.

The terms defined in this document form part of our wider Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE) glossary, [a growing resource on our website](#), which also includes language from our other frameworks and courses. It is a work in progress, and we're adding new sections all the time. As we add new sections, we're also creating PDF records like this one, which you can cite if you find our definitions of terms helpful.

We welcome feedback on the terms included as well as suggestions of additions, and encourage you to [join the conversations](#) in our community of practice.

Related resources

Many of the terms included in this glossary are also defined and expanded upon in these published CSCCE guidebooks:

- Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2020) The CSCCE Community Participation Model – A framework to describe member engagement and information flow in STEM communities. Woodley and Pratt doi: [10.5281/zenodo.3997802](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3997802)
- Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2021) The CSCCE Community Participation Model - Exploring the Champion mode. Woodley and Pratt doi: [10.5281/zenodo.5275270](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5275270)
- Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2022) The CSCCE Community Participation Model - Scaffolding to lower barriers to participation in STEM communities. Woodley, Pratt, and Santistevan doi: [10.5281/zenodo.6078934](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6078934)
- Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2021) The CSCCE Skills Wheel – Five core competencies and 45 skills to describe the role of the community engagement

manager in STEM. Woodley, Pratt, Sandström, Wood-Charlson, Davison, and Leidolf doi:
[10.5281/zenodo.4437294](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437294)

About CSCCE

The Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE) champions the importance of human infrastructure for effective collaboration in STEM. We provide training and support for the people who make scientific collaborations succeed at scale and we also research the impact of these emerging roles.

Find out more about us on our website: cscce.org

Acknowledgements

This sub-section of the glossary was written by CSCCE staff members. CSCCE uses the CRediT contributor roles taxonomy to show how the authors listed contributed to the creation of this guide:

LOU WOODLEY - Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing - Original draft preparation, Writing - Reviewing and Editing

KATIE PRATT - Supervision, Visualization, Writing - Original draft preparation, Writing - Reviewing and Editing

CAMILLE SANTISTEVAN - Writing - Original draft preparation, Writing - Reviewing and Editing

CSCCE Glossary: Scientific Community Engagement Fundamentals

BELONGING

One of four elements that CSCCE emphasizes when considering a **community**. The feeling a community member has that they are somewhere where their presence, identity, and contributions are valued.

CHAMPIONS PROGRAM

A program, usually run by the community manager, that recruits community members to take on tasks and activities designed to advance the mission of the community while also bringing **community champions** together for peer support, training, and/or access to other resources.

CO-CREATE MODE

Most common within established communities, this mode describes how members work together **WITHIN** the community to **CO-CREATE** something that they couldn't do before. For example, community members might organize an event together, form working groups to push the work of the community forward, or establish new communication channels such as a podcast.

This is one of four modes of engagement described in the [CSCCE Community Participation Model](#).

COLLABORATE MODE

In this mode members of a community **COLLABORATE** with one another, often with the community manager providing scaffolding for success but taking a less visible coordinating role. Such collaborations might include co-authoring a white paper or blog post and may involve infrastructure created or maintained by the community manager, but used more independently by community members. For example, there may be general guidelines for writing a guest blog post that the community manager has created, but co-authors work together without the community manager to write the post.

This is one of four modes of engagement described in the [CSCCE Community Participation Model](#).

COMMUNITY CHAMPION

An emergent leadership role within a community in which a community member takes on more responsibility for the success, sustainability, and/or running of the community. Champions may help to maintain, grow, or evolve the community and its mission (see [part 2 of the CSCCE Community Participation Model guidebook](#)).

COMMUNITY LIFECYCLE MODELS

All communities transition through different stages over time. Lifecycle models, of which there are several, describe these transitions and offer insights into why and how they happen.

COMMUNITY OF COMMUNITIES

Some communities are in fact a gathering of representatives from other communities who are coming together at a meta-level to advance a particular agenda in their shared **ecosystem**. Characteristics of these communities might include monthly meetings with limited engagement between those synchronizing sessions, defined and limited membership, and members who belong to more than one community and may be able to act as a bridge between them, sharing news and resources in both directions.

COMMUNITY OVERVIEW STATEMENT

A short, stand-alone description or “executive summary” describing a community or collaboration. Community overview statements include the name of the community, why it exists, who participates in it and what members do together. It also includes information about who convenes the community (e.g., a host organization), the intended lifespan, and whether members connect in person or online.

COMMUNITY: SHARED PURPOSE, BELONGING, CULTURE, AND POWER

A community is a dynamic, social grouping where members align around a shared **purpose** (or multiple overlapping purposes) and participate in a shared **culture**. Active community participation frequently aligns with a sense of **belonging** and affiliation to the community. In a community, the flow of information is multi-directional (i.e., not only flowing out from a source), with members able to do something as a result of being connected to one another that they would not be able to do alone.

CONTENT

Any written, audio or visual materials you make that are related to the functioning of your community. Content includes blog posts, news articles, reports, infographics, photos, videos, podcasts etc.

CONTENT AND PROGRAMMING AUDIT

A careful and methodical assessment of everything you create for your community. It includes factual information about each item, as well as how each product or activity meets the stated goals of the community. The goal of an audit is to determine what you have and whether it’s strategically aligned with the community’s goals, as well as what you might be missing.

CONTENT CALENDAR

A day-by-day, week-by-week, or month-by-month plan of when you are going to share content with your community and via what channel. It can also be used to decide who will create and who will share the content. You can create a content calendar in a spreadsheet, or task management tool such as Trello or Asana.

CONTENT CREATION AND CURATION

Develop, source, and synthesize content including user-generated or original content. Update static content pages. Archive content.

One of the communication skills in the [CSCCE Skills Wheel](#).

CONTENT PILLAR

A strategic or foundational piece of content around which you can build a communications campaign. For example, the release of a new community playbook (your content pillar) will require you to write a related blog post, host a community call to discuss its contents with members, and share it via social media and your newsletter mailing list.

CONTENT PLANNING

Develop a strategy to establish effective themes, templates, and timelines for sharing content with community members and external audiences.

One of the communication skills in the [CSCCE Skills Wheel](#).

CONTENT STRATEGY

The why (desired outcomes), how (platforms, content types, and communications channels), when (timeline), and who (defined audiences) of your communications plan. Your strategy should also include a plan for measuring success, and how you will gather the data for these metrics.

CONTRIBUTE MODE

In this mode, members are empowered to CONTRIBUTE in some way. Often these contributions are invited or facilitated by a community manager, especially in the early stages of a community, and might include presenting on a webinar, writing a guest blog post, or sharing resources on a community platform. One function of the contribute mode is to enable members to discover the skills and interests of others in the group by making knowledge more visible.

This is one of four modes of engagement described in the [CSCCE Community Participation Model](#).

CONVEY/CONSUME MODE

Groups usually begin in this phase, with a community manager or communications professional CONVEYing information for members to CONSUME independently of one another. This might look like a regular newsletter to an email list, social media posts to followers, or other broadcast communications.

This is one of four modes of engagement described in the [CSCCE Community Participation Model](#).

CSCCE COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION MODEL

The [CSCCE Community Participation Model](#) describes four modes of member engagement that can occur within a community – CONVEY/CONSUME, CONTRIBUTE, COLLABORATE, and CO-CREATE – and one that can occur outside of it: CHAMPION. All modes may be present at once, with some members interacting in multiple modes – or a community may have member engagement that falls into only some of the modes described.

CULTURE

One of four elements that CSCCE emphasizes when considering a **community**. The shared values, behaviors, rituals, and artifacts of a group. A community can be thought of as a vessel or container for culture and can enable new behaviors to be established and practiced outside of members' day-to-day contexts. This may then support extension of the new behaviors to those contexts, something Wenger, McDermott, and Snyder refer to in an organizational setting as a "double-knit knowledge organization."

ECOSYSTEM

An ecosystem is a shared environment in which multiple communities may be working on related projects and activities to advance a particular agenda, such as the adoption of open science practices. These communities may have funders, members, clients and/or users in common, and may seek to intentionally align their missions and identify opportunities for collaboration rather than competition.

Note that this is distinct from a software E/ecosystem which is not discussed in the CEF course.

FORMAL CHAMPIONS

Members of a community in champions roles that are recognized with named leadership positions. There may or may not be a champions program to support these individuals.

INFORMAL CHAMPIONS

Members of a community without a named leadership role who nevertheless go above and beyond

in their efforts to advance the mission of the community. These may also be thought of as “super-users.”

MEMBER RESEARCH

The deliberate process of finding out more about your community members. This might include conducting one-on-one interviews, distributing a survey, convening focus groups, or a combination of research activities. Results are curated into a report for your community team and/or leadership, and may or may not also be shared with the community.

MEMBER TYPES

Member types vary by community, but broadly describe the attributes (e.g., career stage, discipline, organization, etc.) of different groups within a community. Describing member types can help guide programming and communications.

MULTIMODAL PROGRAMMING

The importance of providing a range of inclusive, accessible programming options that support community members in engaging in a way that matches their current availability, preferences for engaging, and accessibility needs. Community members’ changing modes of engagement can be influenced by time, interest, and other things happening in their lives (see [CSCCE’s Community Participation Model](#)).

NETWORK-CENTRIC LEADERSHIP

Network-centric leadership is a type of leadership where the goal is to support and empower community members in working together. Network-centric leaders encourage cooperation, seek to distribute resources and power, and are responsive to the needs of community members. For a full description of network-centric leadership, see Andy Robinson’s publication; [“The less visible leader.”](#)

ONBOARDING PATHWAYS

The series of actions usually taken by a community manager or community champions to welcome new members to a community. These can include sharing information about community programming and the community platform as well as a welcome call and/or welcome survey to learn more about the new member’s needs and interests. Onboarding typically consists of several phases as discussed in CSCCE’s [Nurturing Online Communities \(NOC\)](#) course (see **scaffolding**).

PERSONAS

Personas are descriptions of fictional, representative members of your community. They are created by aggregating key characteristics of similar members to create representative descriptions.

POWER

One of four elements that CSCCE emphasizes when considering a **community**. The relative influence and agency an individual may have in a group, which may be based on a combination of implicit and explicit factors. CSCCE emphasizes the importance of recognizing, naming and, wherever possible, counteracting power imbalances. While communities may be places where power imbalances can be temporarily equalized, e.g., as community members work together in CO-CREATE mode, members should recognize that this may or may not be true in other contexts in which they work (see **culture**).

PROGRAMMING

Activities that require sustained, facilitated interactions between members (e.g., events, projects, initiatives). **Content** is required to produce programming. Programming often involves the generation of new content.

PURPOSE

One of four elements that CSCCE emphasizes when considering a **community**. Community members may have a single, shared purpose that the community is aiming to address together, or there may be multiple, related shared purposes within a community. As a community manager, identifying the shared purpose and related activities to support achieving it is crucial. A purpose should be specific rather than too general and precise but not so narrow that it stifles a sense of belonging or member agency e.g., “Advance STEM education” is too broad a purpose, and “Advocate for methodology X at Y institution” may be too narrow. “Sharing resources and knowledge for educators around open education approaches to undergraduate biochemistry education” might be appropriate in this example.

RELATIONSHIP DASHBOARD

A secure database or spreadsheet that tracks a community manager’s interactions with key members of a community. Often the lightweight solution for a community manager when starting or bootstrapping a community, and may be superseded by investing in a customer relationship management (CRM) tool.

SCAFFOLDING

The supportive information, activities, and processes that address barriers to member participation and ensure that all members can access and engage in **community programming** (see [part 3 of the CSCCE Community Participation Model guidebook](#)).

SHARED GOALS

These are the goals that all members of a community or subsection of your community share and value. While each individual will have multiple goals, those that are common across members are the

shared goals of the community. Members' shared goals should align with the purpose of the community.

STAKEHOLDERS

People or organizations outside of your community who have a vested interest in the community's success, which may include benefiting from the activities of the community. Stakeholders might include funders, related communities, or special interest groups.

Use of the word "stakeholder" is a topic of debate, which you can [read more about in this article](#).

TRANSACTIONAL INFORMATION SHARING

In [CSCCE's Community Participation Model](#), member interactions that fall into the transactional information sharing modes are CONTRIBUTE and COLLABORATE. Transactional refers to the fact that the terms of engagement should be made clear to all participants and while they are intended to support a common goal, they are likely to be managed by the convening person or organization. In the case of CONTRIBUTE, it is likely that the convener has created the platform to which a member contributes, e.g., a survey. In COLLABORATE mode, it's likely that the convener has scaffolded the means by which members come together to work on a shared goal, e.g., via templates for a writing sprint.

TRANSFORMATIONAL INFORMATION SHARING

In [CSCCE's Community Participation Model](#), member interactions that fall into the transformational information sharing mode are in the CO-CREATE mode. Transformational refers to the fact that the act of sharing information results in the co-creation of something new, that may or may not be overseen by the community manager.

TRANSMISSIVE INFORMATION SHARING

In [CSCCE's Community Participation Model](#), member interactions that fall into the transmissive information sharing mode are in the CONVEY/CONSUME mode. Transmissive refers to the fact that information is transmitted from one individual e.g., the community manager to others, e.g., community members, with no need or expectation for them to reply.

Citing and reusing this guide

CITATION AND REUSE

“CSCCE Glossary: Scientific Community Engagement Fundamentals” by Lou Woodley, Katie Pratt, and Camille Santistevan is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 (CC BY-SA 4.0) [license](#).

Cite as: Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2025) CSCCE Glossary: Scientific Community Engagement Fundamentals. Woodley, Pratt, and Santistevan doi: [10.5281/zenodo.15359413](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15359413)

Contact the CSCCE for other permissions by emailing info@cscce.org. The CSCCE logo is a trademark of CSCCE.

Please clearly attribute any modified use of this material as “Adapted from an original by the Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE) under a CC BY-SA 4.0 license, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.15359413](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15359413).” We request that the CSCCE logo is clearly visible next to the attribution, that you indicate which is the original text, and include the full citation as described above.

Last updated May 2025